

A two-year retrospective observational study of adverse drug reactions related to intravenous drug formulations

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Abstract

<p>Date Received: 04/12/2020 Date Revised: 05/01/2021 Date Accepted: 20/01/2021</p> <p>Keywords Adverse Drug Reactions, intravenous products, spontaneous report, NCC-PvPI, WHO-UMC causality scale.</p>	<p>Adverse drug reactions are the major obstacles to patient safety and drug therapy monitoring. The present article provides the information on intravenous products induced adverse drug reactions collected by spontaneous reporting method through an established pharmacovigilance wing working under NCC-PVPI in an Adverse Drug reaction monitoring center-Nalgonda, Telangana. A total number of 100 intravenous products induced ADRs were collected from different age groups by observational retrospective study for the year January 2018 to December 2019. Results showed that the most affected age group was 20-29 yrs (28 %). The major contribution of the gender that exposed to ADRs was female- 73 % Most intravenous product induced ADRs reported from the Department of OBG (46 %). Drug: Ceftriaxone-induced ADRs were (38 %). The most frequently reported ADR was fever and chills (56 %). Out of 100 ADRs, one was certain, 90 probable/likely, and the remaining 9 were possible as per the WHO-causality scale. In the present work, most of the ADRs were because of intravenous antibiotics followed by anesthetic agents, antiepileptic drugs, ringer lactate, dextrose normal saline, and H2 blockers.</p>
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Introduction

Adverse drug reactions are unintended and noxious reactions that may lead to mortality of the patients when neglected. There is a need to focus on the complexity of diseases, co-morbid conditions, and complex therapy regimens to avoid unnecessary risks due to ADR and to maintain patient compliance (Claudia *et al.*, 2018).

Intravenous therapy is an important method due to 100 % bioavailability, quick recovery with zero absorption time, and immediate rehydration of the body. It is the needed plan implemented by clinicians in in-patients especially in case of emergencies, surgeries, post-operative phase, and immune support for the patients (Patel *et al.*, 2016; Doshi *et al.*, 2012) Most of the in-patients are in need to use *intravenous* antibiotics, ringer lactate, dextrose normal saline, H2 blockers for prophylaxis therapy, and anesthetic agents for surgeries, antiepileptic drugs for the treatment procedures.

The average amount of antibiotics consumed by 1,000 inhabitants in India per day has been increased by 63 Percent between 2000 and 2015. Compared to the present situation in India, antibiotic consumption increased by 65 per cent and thus the consumption rate per 1,000 inhabitants increased 39 per cent globally (Banjot Kaur, 2019).

The prescription rate of antibiotics in India is 412 prescriptions per 1,000 persons per annum. Approximately, 519 million antibiotic prescriptions were dispensed in India in 2014. However, lies within the incontrovertible fact that when it involves the antibiotic drugs which are third and fourth line, India beats a number of nations. The share of prescriptions with cephalosporin and quinolones (38.2 % and 16.3 %) in India were significantly above the United States (14.0 % and 12.7 %), and Greece (32.9 % and 0.5 %) (Akalu *et al.*, 2017; Richa *et al.*, 2015). The present article explains the effect of ADRs due to various *intravenous* products on patient safety in an Inpatient scenario at an adverse drug reaction monitoring center.

Methods

In the present study, the data were collected retrospectively from the adverse drug reaction monitoring center, Kamineni Institute of medical sciences, Narketpally, Nalgonda, Telangana from Jan 2018 to Dec 2019. During this period, ADRs were collected by spontaneous reporting. The category of *intravenous* products included for the gathering of ADRs were antibiotics, anesthetics, antiepileptics, Ringer Lactate, dextrose normal saline, and H2 blockers as mentioned in **Table 1.** (Bhabhor *et al.*, 2014; Schatz *et al.*, 2015).

Total number of ADRs collected were 100 during the retrospective observational study period. The data was analyzed on a percentage basis. Causality assessment of collected ADRs was done based on WHO-causality scale (Kalaiselvan *et al.*, 2019)

As per **Table 1**, the highest number of ADRs were reported for injection ceftriaxone-38 followed by metronidazole -22 and amoxiclav-14 (Chopra *et al.*, 2014; Ferner *et al.*, 2017; Mushtaq *et al.*, 2014; Dorota *et al.*, 2014).

Results

Table 1: Distribution of ADRs

Intravenous products	Category	ADRs reported	Most frequently reported ADR	Total No of ADRs reported
Amikacin	Aminoglycoside	Cough, fever & chills	Cough	2
Amoxiclav	Beta-lactamase inhibitors	Fever & chills, Erythma on upper limbs, sore throat	Fever, Chills	14
Ceftriaxone	Cephalosporin-bacteriostatic	Fever & chills, tachycarda, Injection site swelling & burning, skin rash, itching, diarrhea, vomiting, nausea, Erythematous drug reaction, itching, speechless, Heartburn	Fever, Chills	40
Cefotaxime	Cephalosporin-bacteriostatic	Pruritus, Fever & Chills, Vomitings, Diarrhea	Fever, Chills	6
Phenytoin	Barbiturates	Itching	Pruritus	1
Piptaz	Penicillin& Beta-lactamase inhibitor	Fever & Chills, Skinrash	Erythematous reaction	7
Rantac	Histamine H2-receptor antagonist	Fever & Chills, oedema of face	Erythematous reaction	1
Metrogyl	Nitroimidazole	Fever & Chills, Headache, Diarrhea, pruritus, Heartburn	Fever,Chills	22
Vancomycin	Glycopeptide	Erythematous reaction, oedema of face	Erythematous reaction	3
Ringer lactate	Electrolyte supplement Caloric	Shortness of breath	Fever,Chills	1
Dextrose normal saline	&electrolyte replenishment	Fever & Chills	Fever,Chills	1
Lignox (Lidocaine+Adrenaline)	Amide local anesthetic and a Class 1b antiarrhythmic agent+ sympathomimetic catecholamine	Severe burning and swelling of injection site	Erythematous reaction	2

Figure 1: Percentage distribution of patients affected based on age group

Age group (20-29 yrs) mostly affected with *i.v.* products induced ADRs followed by age group (30-39 yrs) and (40-49yrs) as shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 2: Percentage distribution of patients affected based on gender

73 % of female patients were affected by ADRs as depicted in **Figure 2**.

Figure 3: Department wise percentage distribution of intravenous products induced ADRs

As shown in **Figure 3**, most of the ADRs were reported from Department-OBG followed by pediatric and general medicine.

Figure 4: Percentage distribution of ADRs based on category of drug

Ceftriaxone and cefotaxime of category cephalosporins collectively contributed 46 % (40 % + 6 %) of the total reported ADRs. Metrogl of category nitroimidazole contributed 22 % of reported ADRs. Amoxiclav of category Beta-lactamase inhibitors contributed 14 % of reported ADRs as depicted in **Figure 4**.

Figure 5: Percentage Distribution of ADRs based on category of adverse reaction.

Fever and chills are the most frequently reported ADRs with a contribution of 56 % followed by erythematous reactions 12 % and injection site swelling 9 % and pruritus 9 % as shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 6: Percentage Distribution of ADRs based on causality.

The causality of ADRs been assessed by the WHO UMC causality scale (Meyboom et al., 1997). ADRs were assigned for causality as 90 % probable/likely, 9% possible, and 1 % certain as depicted in **Figure 6**.

Discussion

All the reported ADRs were non-serious. 73 % of female population and the age group (20-29 yrs) were mostly affected with ADRs. The highest no of ADRs were reported from Department of OBG, however the results were depending upon the no of patients visited to the particular department during the study period (Shamna et

al., 2014). Cephalosporins 46 % reportedly contributed to most of the ADRs as it was prescribed as the first choice of drug for the treatment followed by metrogyl 22 % (Nitroimidazoles) and beta-lactamase inhibitor 14 %. Fever and chills are the frequently reported ADR followed by the cutaneous reactions (Jung et al., 2017; Young-Min et al., 2018). Less number of ADRs were reported for lignox, phenytoin and rantac 1 % which were cutaneous and fever and chills respectively. All the reported ADRs were listed as per package leaflet information and no ADR were reported due to co-morbidity or drug-drug interactions. Most of the ADRs were not preventable as those are of continuation of drug therapy. However, the results of the study may be influenced by the under reporting and gender and number of patients visited the hospital during the study period.

Conclusions

Cephalosporins were the foremost commonly prescribed antibiotic across all diagnoses with the exception of disorders of the urogenital system where quinolones were more commonly prescribed. A survey conducted in south India revealed that above 50 per cent of doctors gave patient satisfaction, time pressure and treatment uncertainty as reasons for prescribing a broad-spectrum antibiotic. Antimicrobial resistance is the ongoing problem which need to be focused to accomplish better patient safety.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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